

Google Tag Manager - Shopify

Google Tag Manager - Shopify Integration

Our research proved that all top Shopify stores use Google Tag Manager, also known as GTM. Shopify doesn't have a native integration with Google Tag Manager. So you either need to use a Shopify app for the GTM integration or you need help from developers and data specialists.

We will touch base on all possibilities on this page and arm you with the information and tools!

[Learn More >](#)

Why use GTM on Shopify

Every piece of data matters in e-commerce. You want to track every possible action such as add-to-cart, add-to-wishlist, purchase, video actions, and many others. Not only to track but you also want to share it with 3rd parties such as Facebook Pixel and Google Ads to get a better ROI with your Ads. GTM is your best friend for all of this.

[Learn More >](#)

How to Set up Google Tag Manager on Shopify?

We are more than happy to show you how you can add the Google Tag Manager container to your Shopify store. As Shopify doesn't have a native integration, there are two options to move on here. We have both video and text tutorials on the following topics:

- ⦿ Method 1: Setup GTM on Shopify editing the code (without an app)
- ⦿ Method 2: Using an app to set up GTM on Shopify

[Learn More >](#)

Shopify Google Tag Manager apps are very important if you want to have a solid, accurate, and in-depth reporting, measuring, and data-processing structure for your store. Google Tag Manager (GTM) is a huge help to collect data and to manage the marketing/tracking tags from one.

[Learn More >](#)

Shopify dataLayer for GTM

dataLayer is one of the most important concepts of the data tracking & analytics topic. We prepared a special code block for you that will allow Google Tag Manager to read/process your purchase data.

[Learn More >](#)

Google Tag Manager - Shopify Course

Google Tag Manager is an essential tool for Shopify stores. It allows you to manage all the marketing/tracking tags from one place - without needing a developer.

That's why we have prepared this FREE Shopify - Google Tag Manager Course. We wanted to give you a complete solution from intro to advanced - using Google Tag Manager for your Shopify store and learning this magical tool, called GTM.

[Learn More >](#)

A Complete GTM Setup

We have a pre-built container that includes all you need.

30+ Pre-Built Tags

FB Pixel, Google Ads, LinkedIn, Twitter, Pinterest, Klaviyo, and many others.

Google Analytics 4

The recently launched GA4 and all cool GA4 features are supported.

Data Analytics Audit & Setup

Audit your current data analytics & set up according to your unique needs.

Shopify App for Data-Analytics

What Analyzify Can Do For Your Store

Analyzify is an all-in-one Shopify data-analytics app that takes care of all of your data collection and tracking needs for your Shopify store.

[Book a Demo](#)

One-Time Fee - Including the App, Setup, Support

Analyzify is a great deal - it doesn't have any ongoing costs. Our price includes the app, custom setup, and world-class support.

\$179

One-time fee per store

[Install Now >](#)

What's included?

- Do-It-Yourself Setup Option
- Done-For-You Setup Option
- Data Analytics Audit & Strategy
- Advanced dataLayers
- Complete GTM Setup
- Google Analytics 4 Setup
- FB Pixel, Ads Conversions
- And 10+ built-in tags

Why do I need a separate app instead of using Shopify native reports? ^

Shopify's native reports will not be enough to run and optimize professional marketing campaigns. Shopify provides you a simple report interface with the most basic data. Shopify's native integration doesn't support Google Tag Manager, Google Analytics 4, and many other related parties. You need an advanced tracking & reporting setup to maximize your ROI.

I don't know anything about Google Tag Manager. Can I still use Analyzify? v

Can you set up everything for me? v

Is Analyzify providing accurate data? v

Can Analyzify be used by non-Shopify Plus stores? v

Free Analyzify GA4 Wizard vs. Analyzify Shopify App v

Shopify already links with Google Analytics & Facebook Pixel. Why would I use Analyzify? v

We have been working with Shopify clients for a long time in data projects. Our clients' needs inspired us to build the Analyzify Shopify App.

Take a Step Forward

- > [Book a 20-mins Demo](#)
- > [Have Questions? Contact Us](#)

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